
106. The remarkable cluster Westerlund 1

WESTERLUND 1 is a young compact star cluster, at a distance of 3–4 kpc, thought to be the most massive young star cluster in our Galaxy. Discovered by Bengt Westerlund in 1961, studies are hampered by its high interstellar absorption: while its brightest stars have $V \sim 14$ mag, none are brighter than $B \sim 19$ mag.

With some 200 members (Clark et al., 2005), a total mass (including gas and dust) of $\sim 60\,000M_{\odot}$, and a radius of ~ 1 pc, it has an estimated age of around 5 Myr.

Today, Westerlund 1 is considered to be an example of the small class of ‘young massive clusters’, dense aggregates of young stars that form the ‘*fundamental building blocks of galaxies*’ (Portegies Zwart et al., 2010). While only a few exist in our Galaxy and the Local Group, they are abundant in starburst and interacting galaxies.

The nearest are of great interest for studying the stellar mass function, and the interplay between stellar evolution and stellar dynamics. And they typically host a wide range of exotic stars and unusual binaries.

WESTERLUND 1 indeed contains many rare, evolved, high-mass stars, including four red supergiants, six yellow hypergiants (with initial masses 20 – 60 M_{\odot}), one of the largest known stars (W237, with $R \sim 1200R_{\odot}$), 24 Wolf–Rayet stars (see essay #105), a luminous blue variable, numerous OB supergiants, an unusual supergiant which may be the remnant of a recent stellar merger (Clark et al., 2005), and the anomalous X-ray pulsar CXO J164710.20–455217, a slow rotating neutron star inferred to have formed from a high-mass ($M \gtrsim 40M_{\odot}$) progenitor (Muno et al., 2006).

Westerlund 1 is believed to have formed through a single burst of star formation, implying that its constituent stars have similar ages and initial compositions. And it is the presence of significant numbers of both Wolf–Rayet stars, and red and yellow supergiants, that provides a strong constraint on its age: theory dictates that red supergiants will only form at ~ 4 Myr, while the Wolf–Rayet population falls off sharply after ~ 5 Myr.

While hosting some of the most massive and least-understood stars in our Galaxy, its great distance means that its detailed properties are still only poorly known.

IN HIS DISCOVERY paper, Westerlund (1961) estimated the cluster’s distance as 1400 pc, based on its assumed location in the Sagittarius arm (further justified by its luminosity function), and its age as ~ 3 Myr, derived from its main sequence turnoff.

None of its stars were observable by Hipparcos, with its limit of $V = 12 - 13$ mag. But there have been several other more recent distance estimates, e.g. based on the assumed intrinsic luminosities of B-supergiants (Crowther et al., 2006), a kinematic distance based on the radial velocity of the H I gas (Kothés & Dougherty, 2007), or fitting of the (pre-)main sequence (Brandner et al., 2008). All have converged on a distance of ~ 4 kpc.

THE FIRST DISTANCE estimates using the Gaia data were made using Data Release 2. But given the large cluster distance, the high star density on the sky, and the limitations of DR2 in terms of the possible parallax zero-point offset, chromaticity calibration, and unrecognised binarity, I shall mention these results only briefly.

Clark et al. (2019) mainly addressed the possible membership of two blue stragglers (Wd1–27 and Wd1–30a). While they derived an average cluster parallax of 0.21–0.24 mas based on other members (and assuming a zero-point offset of -0.05 mas), they could only conclude that their estimate was ‘consistent with previous values’. They also commented that many cluster stars are sufficiently large that their disks may be resolved by Gaia... even at a distance of 4 kpc!

Aghakhanloo et al. (2020) divided the stars into field stars and cluster members based on the observed parallax distribution. They derived a larger mean cluster parallax $\pi = 0.35^{+0.07}_{-0.06}$ mas, and hence a significantly smaller mean distance $d = 2.6^{+0.6}_{-0.4}$ kpc. They argued that such a smaller distance would require an older cluster age, with significant implications for the origins of its many post main-sequence objects.

Davies & Beasor (2019) used a proper-motion selection of spectroscopically-confirmed members, finding $d = 3.87^{+0.95}_{-0.64}$ kpc. Limited by the knowledge of the DR2 zero-point parallax offset, the value was nonetheless close to the ~ 4 kpc found in previous studies.

MORE RELIABLE astrometric data became available with Early Data Release 3 (EDR3) in 2020, and with it some interesting new insights.

Aghakhanloo et al. (2021) repeated the analysis they had made using Gaia DR2 (as noted above), benefiting from a typical improvement in the individual parallaxes of some 30%. Their analysis (which reported densities of cluster stars and field stars of about 150 and 40 stars per square arcmin respectively) gave a mean parallax $\pi = 0.34 \pm 0.05$ mas, corresponding to a distance $d = 2.8^{+0.7}_{-0.6}$ kpc, consistent with their previous result using Gaia DR2, and (let me stress) at variance with the previous consensus. Again, the implications of this closer distance (in terms of lower stellar luminosities, lower turnoff mass, decrease in the total stellar mass, and increase in age) would be significant.

In parallel, Beasor et al. (2021) repeated the analysis of Davies & Beasor (2019), also using the EDR3 parallaxes. They confirmed *their* previous estimates, deriving a mean parallax $\pi = 0.243 \pm 0.027$ mas, corresponding to a distance $d = 4.12^{+0.66}_{-0.33}$ kpc.

However their story adds a further twist: new infrared photometry for their cool supergiants was only consistent with a much older age of $10.4^{+1.3}_{-1.2}$ Myr.

But with an upper age limit inferred from the most massive component of the W13 binary system being significantly younger than the age inferred from the supergiant luminosities (I say a little more on this method below), they concluded that stellar evolution models cannot explain the cluster in the framework of a single age. Instead, they proposed that the stars in the Westerlund 1 region formed over a period of several Myr.

NEXT CAME an independent analysis of the EDR3 data by Negueruela et al. (2022). Together with spectra of a large sample of luminous stars in the surrounding field, they explored the extent of the cluster using a non-parametric analysis of proper motions and membership determination, along with the reddening and proper motions of several dozen OB stars and red supergiants less than a degree away from the cluster centre.

From this they derived a mean cluster distance $d = 4.23^{+0.23}_{-0.21}$ kpc. Their derived extinction increases by a large amount at distances ~ 2.8 kpc, which they attribute to dark clouds associated with the Scutum–Crux arm. In consequence, while they found only a few stars at distances beyond that of the cluster, they identified a second, (astrometrically) well-defined foreground population, at ~ 2 kpc, centred 8 arcmin away, likely connected to the possible open cluster BH 197.

They also concluded that Westerlund 1 is elongated, an effect that they considered as real and not simply a manifestation of the very heavy extinction to the east and south. They also identified a low-density halo extending to angular distances of 10 arcmin from the cluster centre, mainly to the north-west.

LET ME RECALL that independent distance estimates are possible for double-lined spectroscopic binaries which are also resolved by astrometry, and for which both radial velocities and orbital motion can be measured. Going further, dynamical masses can also be determined if the orbit inclination is known, and an upper limit to the cluster's age is then given by the expected lifetime of the most massive binary component.

Of the four massive eclipsing binaries in Westerlund 1 (Wdeb, W13, W36, and WR77o), the two most massive systems, WR77o and W13 are discussed by Beasor et al. (2021), while W36, with $d = 4.03 \pm 0.25$ kpc, is considered in detail by Rocha et al. (2022).

FINALLY, I WILL LOOK at the detailed analysis of the EDR3 astrometry by Navarete et al. (2022).

Starting with 106 previously suggested members, and identifying a further 60 or so based on their EDR3 astrometry and photometry, they constructed colour–magnitude, proper motion, and parallax distributions of both cluster members and field stars (the spatial distribution is shown here). From their 172 inferred members, they derived $d = 4.06^{+0.36}_{-0.34}$ kpc, in good agreement with Beasor et al. (2021).

With this growing consensus on distance, the cluster age is also gaining better clarity. Navarete et al. (2022) derived ages of their red supergiants as 9.7–11.7 Myr, in good agreement with estimates of 9.2–11.7 Myr for the cool supergiant W75 reported by Beasor et al. (2021). Yet their estimated age of the eclipsing binary system W36, ~ 6.5 Myr, is close to the < 5 Myr for the binary system W13 reported by Beasor et al. (2021).

In conclusion, both studies indicate a range of star formation over 5–12 Myr. This is in line with recent rotating and non-rotating (Geneva) models by Yusof et al. (2022) who were able to broadly reproduce the observed population of red supergiants, yellow hypergiants, and Wolf–Rayet stars. Further optimisation in terms of mass-loss and binary interactions are nonetheless indicated.

TWENTY FIVE years after the release of the Hipparcos catalogue, which contained *no stars* of the Westerlund 1 cluster, the Gaia EDR3 catalogue, based on just the first 34 months of mission data, is providing a fundamentally new view of this highly obscured cluster at a distance of some 4 kpc.

Future Gaia catalogues, with better astrometry, better control of its systematics, and better information on binarity, will surely bring still deeper insights into the properties of this most remarkable Milky Way cluster.

Navarete et al. (2022)